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Civilian Protection in the Gaza–Israel Conflict: An Analysis of UN News through the Lens of International Humanitarian Law

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Abstract

Media narratives shaped by selective or biased perspectives can obscure realities on the ground, making objective reporting essential in times of conflict. This study presents a content analysis of United Nations News coverage of the Gaza–Israel conflict over a six-month period, examining news stories published from 7 October 2023 to 30 March 2024. This study aims to investigate the extent to which themes of neutrality, peace building, humanitarian concern, and bias are reflected in UN News reporting. More specifically, the research offers an in-depth examination of how UN News portrays the conflict, with particular attention to the victimization and protection of civilians. The analytical framework is grounded in international humanitarian law, especially the principles outlined in Geneva Convention IV and Additional Protocol I. These legal provisions provide the basis for organizing and analyzing news content related to civilians and population, property, and treatment during armed conflict. The study focused the United Nations' perspective on civilian protection and its condemnation of violations as reported by an official international platform committed to humanitarian principles. The sampled news items are organized into three main dimensions, civilians and population, property, and treatment, along with sub-themes drawn from Geneva Convention IV and broader principles of international humanitarian law. Using both qualitative and quantitative content analysis, the study also applies agenda-setting and framing perspectives to examine language, tone, textual patterns, and the overall emphasis of coverage. The findings show that UN News framed the Gaza–Israel conflict mainly through a humanitarian and international humanitarian law perspective, emphasizing civilian protection, aid, ceasefire, and condemnation of brutality. At the same time, although neutrality and peacebuilding remained visible, the coverage also reflected limited subjectivity, particularly in its stronger emphasis on Palestinian suffering and, at times, Israeli victims and hostages.

Keywords: Gaza–Israel conflict, United Nations News, international humanitarian law, Geneva Convention IV, protection of civilians, agenda-setting, framing

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Introduction

This paper attempts to explore particular perspective of United Nations on recent Gaza-Israel conflict 2023 reflecting through its media content. It is sine-qua-non (Objective) to critically examine or assess the media's impartiality or biasness, objectivity or subjectivity over issue applying appropriate neutral frames and when such media is mouth-piece of world's recognized International Body "United Nations Organization" so exploration becomes inevitable to empirically understand causes of forming public opinion and narrative-building related to any particular perspective. In order to understand the UN perspective on Gaza-Israel recent Conflict with focus on protection of civilian persons, population, property and administration, this study examines UN News reports through the prism of international human rights law (IHL). The framework for this study is designed in way to examine the portrayal or visibility of impartiality, objectivity, peacemaking, and humanitarian effects in UN Media coverage on Gaza-Israel Conflict. The 1949 Fourth Geneva Convention on the Protection of Civilians in Time of War is a major piece of composed international law in the area of humanitarian assistance (Clapham et al., 2015). Its goal is to guarantee that, even in the midst of conflict, the universally acknowledged principle of human dignity will be upheld without exception (Henckaerts & Alvermann, 2005).

Glimpses of Palestine-Israel Conflict

Tracing the backdrop of the ongoing war in Gaza, this devastation and the mounting death toll have accelerated protests around the world, bringing this decades-old issue to the center stage of world politics. The Israeli-Palestinian conflict has deep historical roots, starting from events such as the Balfour Declaration, the UN Partition Plan and the Oslo Accords. The current conflict has led to the Killing, displacement of Palestinians. Israel-Palestinian settlements in the West Bank and the blockade of Gaza, affecting millions of people in the region (Ahmed et al., 2014). The British government's endorsement of the creation a a "national home of the Jewish people" in Gaza was signalled by the 1917 Balfour Declaration, according to historical accounts. This proclamation laid the groundwork for Israel's founding in 1948, which made it a significant factor in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict ('What's the Israel-Palestinian Conflict about and How Did It Start?', 2023). Studies have shown that media discourse and educational narratives play an essential role in developing civic consciousness and social justice orientations among audiences (Gul et al., 2023; Ahmad & Gul, 2021). Israel was founded in 1948 after the UN Separation Plan of 1947 split Palestine's territory into distinct Jewish and Arab governments. Palestinians were forced to relocate as a result of this scheme, which is known as the Nakba (Chughtai, n.d.). The Nakba refers to the mass displacement of over 750,000 Palestinians from their homes by Zionist militias that led to the establishment of Israel in 1948. This event has had a lasting impact on the Palestinian people and remains an important aspect of the Israeli- Palestinian (Gelvin, 2014). Yasser Arafat, the leader of Palestine, and Yitzhak Rabin, the prime minister of Israel, signed the Oslo Accords in 1993 with the intention of splitting the West Bank in three distinct parts and achieving peace within five years. However, the breakdown of the Oslo Accords was influenced by the continued growth of Israeli settlements in Palestinian territories, which caused constant tensions in the region (Chughtai, n.d.). Such events played an important role in the current Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Regarding the war between Gaza and Israel, Israeli settlements in the West Bank and East Jerusalem have grown from about 250,000 settlements in 1993 to 700,000 in 1993, Al Jazeera news channel reported, leading to the Oslo the collapse of

the Agreement. The settlements are considered illegal under international law and have been

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condemned by the United Nations as a major obstacle to the establishment of a viable Palestinian state through a "two-state solution." (Chughtai, n.d.).

Israel's blockade of Gaza is an important aspect of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. It has been in force since 2007 and has had a serious impact on the lives of approximately 2 million Palestinians living in the Gaza Strip. The blockade restricts the movement of people and goods in and out of Gaza, causing economic hardship, limited access to essential services, and a humanitarian crisis in the region. The blockade has been widely criticized by the international community for its impact on the civilian population and their basic human rights. Such impediments, hostilities, constant deprivation caused serious concerns by giving rise to the unending situations in region and current conflict with its long-lasting devastation is an evident of such miseries. Media narratives and framing significantly shape public perceptions regarding conflict situations and humanitarian crises, influencing how audiences interpret events and construct meaning from news coverage (Gul & Khilji, 2021; Ahmad & Gul, 2021). Media coverage plays a crucial role in shaping public understanding of conflict, humanitarian responsibility, and justice. The Responsibility to Protect (R2P) framework also recognizes the media's importance in raising awareness of global crises and influencing both public opinion and decision-makers toward action (Rimmer, n.d.; Michelis, 2018). In the context of the Gaza-Israel conflict, media representations can either reinforce bias and violent narratives or promote impartiality, peace-oriented reporting, and humanitarian concern. Previous scholarship suggests that coverage of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict is often shaped by political and ideological agendas, making objective and peace-focused journalism essential for a fuller understanding of the conflict (Morris, 2019). Media narratives also affect civic engagement and perceptions of justice, which further highlights the significance of examining how conflicts are reported (Gul et al., 2023; Gul, Batool, Khan, & Jabeen, 2023). In this context, the present study aims to examine the visibility of bias, neutrality, peace-building, and humanitarian aspects in UN News coverage of the Gaza-Israel conflict, while also exploring the media's role in portraying an impartial understanding of war. Against this background, the study asks: To what extent are bias, neutrality, peace-building, and humanitarian concerns visible in UN News coverage, and how does UN News address the Gaza-Israel conflict while seeking to uphold the principles of impartiality and humanitarianism?

Literature Review

Portrayal of Gaza-Israel Conflict 2023 in UN News & Principles of IHL

The Hamas attacks on Israel and the resulting Israeli bombing campaign in the Gaza Strip have sparked debate over the extent to which international humanitarian law - the law that governs armed conflict, military operations and occupation - applies to the current situation between Israel and Israel. and Israel. Palestinian armed groups (How Does International Humanitarian Law Apply in Israel and Gaza?, 2023). According to the report published on 14th May 2024, After nearly eight months of recent devastating Palestine-Israel conflict, more than 10,000 people are believed buried under the rubble in Gaza, according to the UN Humanitarians, citing the enclave's health authorities (10,000 People Feared Buried under the Rubble in Gaza | UN News, 2024). Continuous Israeli bombardment has crippled humanitarian aid deliveries and life. Nearly 360,000 people

have fled Rafah, according to the statement of UN agency for Palestinian refugees, UNRWA (Rafah Exodus| UN News, 2024). Social and psychological responses to crisis situations are shaped by collective perceptions, leadership narratives, and institutional communication

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strategies (Zhou, Gul, & Tufail, 2022). The U.N. agency said one in five Gaza residents has been forcibly displaced in the past week alone. The United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) said "civilians must be protected and their basic needs met, whether they move or stay." Those leaving should be given adequate time, as well as safe routes and safe place to go (Israeli Bombardment Continues | UN News, 2024). Geneva (ICRC) - The International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) warned in February that a major Israeli military operation in Rafah would pose a disastrous risk to civilians, given the more than 1 million displaced Palestinians now living in the south of the Gaza Strip (Gaza, 2024). Research in educational psychology and social behavior highlights that exposure to humanitarian narratives can strengthen empathy, civic awareness, and ethical responsibility among audiences (Gul et al., 2023). IHL, the area of international law that focusses on limiting the use of force in armed conflict, makes a distinction between those who are directly involved in hostilities and those who are not (CIHL 1999). This idea or clause leads to the fundamental idea of IHL, which emphasizes:

Distinguish between civilians and combatants,

It is prohibited to attack a person who is hors de combat,

Do not cause unnecessary suffering.

Violence is not prohibited,

It cannot protect all people affected by armed conflict,

It is not allowed to prevent one side from defeating the enemy.

Assume the legitimate objectives of the parties.

For thousands of years, various forms of laws related to war, including International Humanitarian Law (IHL), have been in existence. However, the modern version of IHL emerged in the Geneva Convention of 1949, along with other treaties and customary international law. IHL applies to both states, such as Israel, and non-state armed groups involved in conflicts like Hamas and Islamic Jihad. Although these groups can not formally endorse treaties, they are still bound by IHL principles (IHL, 2023).

The essential requirement that all parties engaged in a conflict make a distinction between civilians and combatants is the cornerstone of international humanitarian law (IHL). It is highly forbidden to attack citizens or civilian-related objects. Parties may only use force to attack other fighters and military objectives. Declaring that people fail to meet the intended targets is insufficient. All parties are required by international humanitarian law to take all reasonable measures to prevent injury to civilians and civilian property. Furthermore forbidden are any attacks that do not distinguish between civilians and combatants or that are anticipated to inflict disproportionate damage on the civilian population relative to the military gain.(IHL, 2023). During an armed conflict, many different types of people and property are protected by international humanitarian law. Those not immediately engaged in battle are protected by the Geneva Conventions or their Additional Protocols, including the ill, injured, shipwrecked, prisoner of war, detainees, civilians, and civilian objects (IHL, 2016).

Provision of Additional Protocols & Geneva Convention IV

How paradoxical it is, that when armed conflict is continued to be waged around world, the increased number of sufferers are the immune entity "Civilian Population" (CIHL, 1999). In order to display more humanity in armed conflicts, IHL with its other related

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treaties are needed to be examined and through media it is needed to be disseminated to avoid reprisals and brutality against most vulnerable objects in war or armed conflicts. Articles dealing with the “The Protection of the Civilian Population against effects of hostilities” enumerated in [Rule 7 of CIHL] and Article 48 to Article 79. This IV Part of Additional Protocol to Geneva Convention, 1949 consists of 3 sections. Section I containing 6 chapters, Section II and Section III Contains 3 Chapters. The clauses of the Additional Protocol to General Convention 1949 emphasize that disputing parties must uphold the protection of civilians and civilian property. Parties are required to make distinctions between combatants and civilians as well as between military goals and non-combatants (Henckaerts & Alvermann, 2005), IHL, 2016). According to the statute, every individual civilian and civilian population shall not be the object of attack (act of violence) such acts or threats to terrorize civilians are prohibited. General protection shall be enjoyed by civilians unless they take direct part in hostilities (Art-50-51) (Clapham et al., 2015) (Persons protected by international humanitarian law, 2016). All indiscriminate attacks (not directed against specific military objectives) against civilians in the form of reprisals are prohibited (IHL Rule 11). Provisions on the general protection of civilian objects (Article 52) (IHL Rule 8), the protection of cultural property (Article 53), the protection of objects necessary for the survival of civilians (Article 54) and the prevention of starvation for the purpose of depriving civilians of their lives, and have the motive to cause harm to them, is a serious war crime and is strictly prohibited. Protection of the natural environment, works and installations and precautions in the event of attack and other necessary provisions (Articles 62-67) relating to civil defense organizations of neutral States, other States and international coordinating organizations concerning civil defense mechanisms ((Clapham et al.) et al., 2015). Principles and provisions of IHL and Additional Protocol to Geneva Convention part IV are helpful in forming the basis of this stated study. In the light of IHL using reference of APGC-IV, the three main dimensions for selecting news stories are assimilated – civilian population, property and administration/ treatment during war. This selection of dimensions (in UN news), with the reference of Geneva Conventions, is also helpful in further exploration. Such As data related to GAZA-ISRAEL Conflict in UN News is in massive amount. Through using IHL Lens particularly with the view point to examine UN stories in context of war crimes against civilian population, property and administration forms the basis on this study. In the light of IHL and ADGC, Humanitarian aspect, and dimensions for data collection & analysis in the study are set.

Theoretical Framework

In this research for fulfilling the requirements, application of framing theory is considered significant understanding the perspective of UN News with the lens of IHL. Framing theory which speculates that the media plays a crucial role in drawing attention to specific events and subsequently contextualizing them within a field of meaning. This theory’s application here suggesting that the presentation of information or portrayal, known as “the frame,” has a significant impact on how individuals process and interpret that information (Framing Theory | Mass Communication Theory, n.d.). Framing processes not only affect interpretation of media content but also shape attitudes toward social justice, civic responsibility, and collective action (Ahmad, Gul, & Zeb, 2022; Gul et al., 2022). In

order to help structure and organize the meaning that messages convey, frames are used as abstract constructions. Frames are frequently used in media and news coverage because it is thought that they influence how the audience perceives the news (Li, 2012) (Framing Theory | Mass Communication Theory, n.d.). News dissemination through UN contains a

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host of humanistic occurrences, here in this research, particularly analyzing Gaza-Israel conflict, Protection of civilians and related concerns are paramount to be studied and analyzed using humanitarian lenses to determine the actual perception or meaning reflecting and interpreting from message.

Methodology

In order to determine the appropriate technique for fulfilling the objective of this study, Qualitative Content Analysis is applied with systematically quantifying the data into categories. Qualitative content analysis emphasizes an integrated view of the speech/text and its specific context, which helps reveal the meaning of the text. It enables researchers to understand social reality in a subjective yet scientific manner (Zhang & Wildemuth, 2009). Qualitative approaches are particularly useful for understanding complex social narratives and perceptions surrounding conflict, social stress, and institutional responses (Ahmad, Gul, & Kashif, 2022). Collected material is systematically categorized and recorded so that they can be analyzed using qualitative content analysis method by using quantitative approach with more specifications to systematically measure the News and aspects. This study deliberates in-depth examination of UN News stories portraying this recent conflict between Israel and Gaza through the lens of International Humanitarian Law containing the provisions of Additional Protocols I, Geneva Convention IV based on protection of civilian persons and population. Provision in relation to civilian persons and population, property and treatment is used to determine the UN perspective, denunciation, and instance about these issues reflected and reported by a platform or organization forming public opinion. For conducting content analysis, systematic unitizing (Frame-wise segmentation of UN News, Headlines, Sub-headlines, Language of texts), sampling (selection of appropriate Units for analysis) with set of specifications about news examination is designed according to Frames of Protection of Civilians and Administration clauses. Multiple resources are recruited and accessed for data Collection, extraction and coding according to themes and identified categories. Qualitative content analysis was employed and sampled items were structured into three dimensions: Civilian Persons & Population (Hors de combat), Property and Administration, in accordance with the explicit theme revealed in Geneva Convention IV. Civilian persons and population frame intended that the theme of news stories and reports explicitly rather than implicitly covered or embodied (Li, 2012) civilian and population-based issues. Frequency was calculated on the number of stories pertaining to the three major frames to assess and analyze the visibility of Biasness, Neutrality, Peacekeeping, and Humanitarian Effects in News. Frequency analysis assists to understand how often certain values of a variable may occur and to assess the reliability of the prediction. It is a tool for determining.

Data Collection

Data for this study is collected from subscribing the official website of UN News containing world-wide stories related to number of issues happening around the globe from the website United Nations “UN News” with subtitle “Global Perspective Human Stories”. Purposive sampling techniques were adopted, and data is drawn from the main search section of the UN News Website excluding all other additional sections and categories of news having no nexus with specified research area. The particular data required for this study is taken out from Humanitarian Aid, Peace & Security, Women, Culture & Education, Human Rights, Law, and Crime Prevention fields under title of “6

Months stories on Gaza-Israel Conflict”. Amongst a host of search results, stories on stated conflict are collected since 7th October 2023, the day exactly the on-going conflict started.

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Middle East as particular region with specifications of years and months were used to formulate the systematic sample size.

UN News stories published on website contain number of media types including sound cloud interviews, Features, UN Photo Stories, and News in Brief, You Tube UN Videos, Meetings coverage and UN Web TV. In this study, published stories on website were assembled and unitized in Frame-wise categories in accordance with the provision of Geneva Convention IV, Protection of civilians in time of war. Following table includes the set criteria for sampling & data collection as unit of analysis based on civilian persons and population in accordance with Geneva Convention IV.

Table 1. Sampling and Data Collection Criteria Based on International Humanitarian Law (Geneva Convention IV and Additional Protocol I)

Category	Subcategory	Indicators for Sampling and Analysis
Civilian persons and population	Civilian casualties	News reports on the killing, injury, and suffering of Palestinian and Israeli civilians
	Women	Reports concerning women, including killings, injuries, sexual violence, rape, pregnancy-related vulnerability, detention, torture, and degrading treatment
	Children	Reports focusing on children affected by conflict, including death, injury, displacement, detention, and denial of protection
	Vulnerable civilian groups	Reports concerning refugees, journalists, stateless persons, detainees, and other protected civilian groups
Civilian property	Civilian infrastructure	Destruction of houses and other civilian property
	Protected zones and facilities	Attacks on or destruction of safety zones, neutralized zones, hospitals, schools, and shelters
	Cultural property	Destruction of cultural property, heritage sites, and protected cultural objects
	Objects indispensable to civilian survival	Destruction of food supplies, water facilities, agricultural resources, and other objects indispensable for the survival of civilians
Administration and treatment	Protection and treatment of civilians	Reports on the treatment, care, and protection of civilians during the conflict
	Humanitarian aid and relief activities	Reports on aid to the wounded, sick, displaced, detained, and shelter less, including food, shelter, medical assistance, and legal support
	UN resolutions and civil defense	Reports on UN resolutions and the role of civil defense organizations in protecting civilians from hostilities and disasters, including warning, evacuation, rescue, medical services, firefighting, and public safety services

Note. The sampling categories were developed in light of the protections afforded to civilians under Geneva Convention IV and Additional Protocol I of international humanitarian law.

Table 2. Month-Wise Distribution of Sampled UN News Stories on the Gaza–Israel Conflict

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(October 2023–March 2024)

S. No.	Period	Number of News Stories / Reports
1	7 October–31 October 2023	31
2	1 November–30 November 2023	26
3	1 December–31 December 2023	11
4	1 January–31 January 2024	37
5	1 February–29 February 2024	47
6	1 March–30 March 2024	47
Total		199

The sample consists of *UN News* stories selected from relevant categories related to humanitarian aid, peace and security, women, culture and education, human rights, law, and crime prevention.

Stage 1: All *UN News* stories and reports published during the six-month study period were collected separately, resulting in a total sample of 199 items.

Stage 2: The stories from each month were compiled and classified according to the predefined analytical frames: civilian persons and population, civilian property, and administration and treatment. Relevant data were extracted from the main stories in chronological order and according to thematic field.

Stage 3: Separate monthly drafts were prepared containing date-wise headlines and sub-headings for textual analysis. Parallel drafts were also created for photo-story analysis. The data were then systematically extracted and organized statement by statement for further interpretation.**

Data Analysis

Data Analysis commenced with applying more specifications in collected data of 199 news stories from six months. The framework was designed for Qualitative Content Analysis containing stages of further extraction of news stories. The mechanism of the sample was structured on three dimensions: civilian people and population (Hors de combat), property and administration, in accordance with the explicit theme revealed in the IV Geneva Convention. The civilian and population framework intended the subject matter of news and reports to cover or incorporate explicitly, rather than implicitly, civil and population issues. The frequency was calculated based on the number of stories belonging to the three main frames-Positive, Negative and Neutral with Sub-categories (Pro-Palestinian & Pro-Israeli aspects) to evaluate and analyze the visibility of bias, neutrality, peacekeeping and humanitarian effects in the news. Qualitative content analysis after incorporating above thematic categorization was conducted in following manner:

Headlines, Sub-Heads & Text based Analysis (sentences, context, terms, Statements)' collected data is further extracted in accordance with the categories designed for analysis. The systematic data collection with sequential categorization and extraction made it easy to separately analyze the visibility of biasness, neutrality, peacekeeping, Humanitarian, Denunciation perspectives. Analytical Framework designed for this study is given below along with detailed description of operationalization of frames and description of considerations for deciding biasness.

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Table 3. Analytical framework for examining the visibility of bias, neutrality, peace building, and humanitarian perspectives in UN News coverage

Unit of Analysis	Frame Type	Illustrative Indicator
Civilian persons and population (<i>hors de combat</i>)	Positive frame	Humanitarian aid, peacebuilding measures, humanitarian concern, genocide prevention, ceasefire calls, warning alerts, denunciation of brutality, lifesaving interventions, and empathetic solutions
	Negative frame	Bias, subjectivity, reprisals by parties to the conflict, indiscriminate attacks, malicious intent, attacks on civilian property and safety zones, escalating war crimes, destabilization, and suppression
	Neutral frame	Balanced viewpoint, collective responsibility, collective damage, emphasis on peace, and remedial or corrective approaches
Overall media orientation	Evaluative dimension	Degree of visibility of bias, neutrality, peacebuilding, and humanitarian perspective

A **Positive Story** includes overall tone or prevailing elements in the story including tendencies towards Humanitarian Aid, Peace-building Measures, Voicing Humanitarian Concerns, Prevention of Genocide, Ceasefire Calls, Denunciation of Brutality, and Lifesaving Initiatives, stability and Imploring Empathetic Solution for the Gaza-Israel Conflict which tend to contribute or show the manner of Gaza-Israel Conflict's coverage with analyzing the meaning of messages in News stories as a whole. Addition of Pro- Israeli and Pro-Palestinian aspects provides the inclination towards parties to the conflict.

A **Negative Story** includes overall tone or prevailing elements in the story including Biasness/ Subjectivity, Reprisals by Party/ Parties, Indiscriminate Invasion/ Attacks, Malicious Intentions, Escalating War Crimes, Destabilization of Party, Disheartenment, instability, Dominance and other related problems. Such categorization with specification tends to determine the actual sense or perspective latent in the meaning of messages. Pro- Israeli and Pro-Palestinian aspects provide the inclination towards parties in a conflict.

A **Neutral Story** includes overall tone or prevailing elements in the story is either a balance of Positive or Negative, or Mixed with Balanced Viewpoint, Collective Responsibility, Collective Damage, Undermining Collective Peace, and Redressed & Remedial Approach. The criteria for assessing tendencies in applied frames is referred and cited from the literature "'Analysis of China's Comparative Framework Based on ABC and SBS Current Affairs Programs" (Li, 2012). Based on existing literatures, the stated criterion is established for analyzing this study.

The article examines UN News coverage of the Gaza-Israel conflict from an International Humanitarian Law perspective, using framing theory and qualitative content analysis. Explores bias, neutrality and humanitarian aspects in the news, emphasizing the

importance of considering subjectivity when reporting on conflicts. The analysis reveals a

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mix of positive, negative and neutral narratives, with a focus on humanitarian aid, peacebuilding efforts and civil protection. A consideration for Deciding Biasness in News Reflection of Biasness or subjectivity in UN news stories is decided to be considered in accordance with the provisions of IHL APGC. In order to determine (objective) the visibility of Biasness, Neutrality, peace-keeping and humanitarian aspects three main Frames are set- positive, Negative & Neutral with sub-frames/ themes Pro-Palestinian and Pro-Israeli in Positive and Negative aspects. Considerations to decide biasness, humanitarian, peace-building aspects are based on the text tone, language and overall inclinations towards each aspect. Some stories with peaceful and humanitarian aspects are inclined towards Israeli instance (Related to release of Hostages, condemnation for Hamas-led terror attack, Reports on Sexual abuse with Israeli abducted female civilians etc) and many stories includes the empathetic incline towards Palestinian sufferings along with glorifying their miseries due to indiscriminate attacks of Israeli bombardment. Such hostilities of both parties (Hamas & Israeli militants) caused a great amount of civilians casualties. Such act of violence with malicious intentions cause grave breach of war crimes against international humanitarian law. Parties involved in war crimes must be marked or highlighted according to the violence committed by each party in frame settings. Generally, stories are assessed according to three main frames. Pro-Palestinian and Pro-Israeli themes with specific inclination towards any side are the determination point for considering humanitarian aspects specifically. Humanitarian activities including appeals for aids, UN resolutions, for both sides is neutral incline with Balanced Viewpoint, Collective Responsibility, Collective Damage, Undermining Collective Peace, Redresser & Remedial Approach

Results & Discussion

Analyzing Biasness, Neutrality, Peacekeeping, Humanitarian Effects in 199 UN News stories/ reports, visibility of frames, applied under IHL, was also analyzed. Addressing the visibility of frames with extensive textual analysis the finding showed, that during 1st month of conflict (OCTOBER 2023 from 31 news stories) 42% positive inclined, 16% Positive Pro-Palestinians (includes humanitarian aid assistance with prompt security and peace measures for Palestinians) and 16% Negative Pro-Israeli stories (Subjective, Biased, with strong condemning the Hamas-led terror attack) were published.

October 2023 UN News Stories

More specifically quantifying the analysis of extracted data which includes 120 Statements related to civilians and protection, 25 populations, 13 Females (Sexual violence, pregnancy, Rape related), 22 refugees, 16 displaced, 8 Journalists, 18 schools, hospitals respectively, 7 hostilities, 9 de-escalations, 17 shelters aid, 25 Food aid /crisis, 4 related to child stories published. Such statements include 100 condemning act of Hamas (Stating “Hamas-led Terror Attack” etc.) and 9 indiscriminate attacks of both parties in a conflict. Approximately 510 statements maximum with context were considered relevant with explicitly showing the inclination towards set frames. Extending humanitarian aid and peace-building measures in the region for both parties to the conflict, ‘Both deserve to live in peace’ was emphasized. “Civilians bear brunt of violence”. Similar patterns of empathetic framing and social concern have been observed in studies examining civic engagement and social justice narratives in educational contexts (Ahmad & Gul, 2021; Gul et al., 2023). Calling parties to the Israel-Palestine conflict for taking concrete precautionary measures to avoid civilian casualties, intensifying the long-running crisis of all sides. Visibility of Neutrality with peacekeeping efforts and humanitarian assistance

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prevailed while biasness and subjectivity for condemning Hamas- Israeli militants was also explicitly reflected.

Data analysis of 2nd Month (NOVEMBER 2023, 26 NS/R) showed that 61% Positive (Humanitarian Aid, Peace-building initiative, raising humanitarian concerns, Prevention of Genocide, constant condemnation of brutality, Ceasefire, Warnings... etc. related) news published pertaining great concerns on humanitarian grounds. Concerns contained text reflects the clear perspective of UN through its media by making “Call for a “humanitarian ceasefire” or “humanitarian pause” to enable safe delivery of aid for desperate civilians”, “True humanitarian ceasefire' needed”, “Stocks depleting fast”. 31 % News reflected Pro-Palestinian instances (Subjective Reporting having visibility of favorability with Palestinians). “Gaza is on the brink of running out of food, water, electricity and critical supplies”, 8% News contains Neutral aspects “Nothing less than collective punishment” and overall analysis shows that the news inclination towards positive aspects were given more coverage and overall, the neutrality was also visible with subjectivity over humanitarian concerns.

Data analysis of 3rd Month (DECEMBER 2023, 11 NS/R) showed that 18% Positive (Humanitarian Aid, Peace-building initiative, raising humanitarian Concerns, Prevention of Genocide, constant condemnation of brutality, Ceasefire, Warnings... etc. related) news published pertaining great concerns on humanitarian grounds while similar 18% Neutral and Positive Pro-Palestinian trend reflected in UN news with taking concrete measures to provide all humanitarian assistance. Subjectivity carrying Pro-Palestinian stance was highly evident with 46% inclined showing the empathetic viewpoint for major inflicted party (Civilian persons & population) is saddled with unwanted conflict. The Pro-Palestinian statements such as, "Gaza is being strangled", "Gazans: Tantamount to a death sentence", "No place is safe in Gaza anymore" by giving emphasis about the constant airstrike and bombardment by Israeli forces which made life utterly miserable for Palestinians in Gaza. Language and text used in News stories "Gaza is now hell on Earth." "Saving humanity from hell today means for the UN to save Palestinians in Gaza," referring the latent meaning and context of the statements to give realization for collective efforts to stop brutality. From DECEMBER, approximately 281 extracted statements were analyzed separately after examining Headlines, sub-headlines and overall text of News.

Analysis comprised from JANUARY 2024, 37 News Stories /Reports resulted 36% incline towards Positive Aspect containing “No more ‘empty statements...."We must abandon double standards and translate compassionate words into action," 10% Negative, 16% Neutral trend in News by stating “Take ‘real measures’ to cement peace”, while 3% positive Pro- Palestinian, 7% subjectivity and biasness for Israeli victims was described in statements “Israel in deep trauma” condemning the heinous attacks by Hamas, confirms the right of Member States to self-defense and calls on parties to respect international humanitarian law. Statements “No words' for evil of Hamas”, and “There are no words in any language to describe the evil; it has no place in humankind” clearly portraying the inclining perspective towards Pro- Israeli stance. Analysis also shows 29% incline is evidently visible for subjectivity with empathy towards Palestinian civilians. Such subjectivity or biasness could be seen in statements such as “This madness must be brought to an end”, “Gaza: ‘Hospitals are not battlegrounds’, children’s suffering must stop”.

From January, approximately 498 extracted statements were considered relevant for analyzing content after examining Headlines, sub-headlines and overall text of News.

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Data driven and analyzed from 5th Month (FEBRUARY, 47 News Stories/ Reports) of Gaz-Israel Conflict, 32% positive, 6% Negative, 13% Neutral, 6% positive pro-israeli, 2% positive pro Palestine, 4% subjectivity for israelis, 36% subjectivity for Palestinian civilians and population. Reflection and perspective forming public perception over this conflict can be construed by statements such as:

“West showing ‘blatant double standards’ over Gaza”,

“This is not a war; this is a carnage that no one can justify. It must be brought to an end”,

“Conditions for effective aid delivery ‘no longer exist” – Guterres.

Results taken out from 6th Month (MARCH, 47 News Stories/ Reports) of Gaza-Israel Conflict describe the inclination of 36% positive aspect in UN News with 32% subjectivity towards Pro-Palestinian sufferings & losses of civilian’s lives, Property destruction and ill-treatment due to constant blockade and devastation. Results also contain 13% Neutrality aspect with condemning Israeli-Hamas militants for causing unremitting long-lasting damage and undermining collective peace. Results showing 6% Negative aspect based partial stories against Israeli indiscriminate invasion and similarly 6% Positive Pro-Palestinian aspect containing humanitarian assistance taking peace and security measures by calling immediate aid for victims, and appeal for pausing catastrophic acts. 4% positive and 2% negative pro- Israeli results depicting the measures and instance by UN well reflecting in its news with subjectivity towards israeli hostages under control of Hamas militants. This tendency in news showing the denunciation of Hamas-led attack in escalation of ongoing conflict.

Conclusion

This study examined the UN Perspective reflected from the News stories and reports covering the ongoing Gaza-Israel Conflict. The results of extensive Qualitative content analysis with amalgamation of Quantitative approach highlighting several humanities-ridden perspectives. It is also examined through this study that the immense realization for maintaining collective peace and harmony, media's subjectivity towards peace- building and humanitarian initiatives is considered indispensable. It is witnessed that when armed conflict is continuing to be waged around world, the increased number of sufferers are the immune entity “Civilian Population” In order to display more humanity in armed conflicts, IHL with its other related treaties are needed to be examined and through media it is needed to be disseminated to avoid reprisals and brutality against most vulnerable objects in war or armed conflicts.

Based on the results and discussion of the study analyzing the UN perspective on the Gaza-Israel conflict through UN News stories, it is evident that there is a significant focus on humanitarian aspects, neutrality and the denunciation of actions that undermine peace and security. Content analysis revealed a mix of positive, negative and neutral aspects in the report, with a notable inclination to highlight the suffering of Palestinian civilians and the need for immediate humanitarian aid. The study successfully applied qualitative and quantitative content analysis to assess bias, neutrality, peacekeeping, and humanitarian effects in news coverage. Through a systematic approach to data collection and analysis, the study provided valuable insights into how the United Nations frames and portrays the ongoing conflict, shedding light on the complexities and challenges faced in maintaining peace and protecting to civilian populations. The findings reinforce the argument that communication narratives and educational perspectives can influence civic awareness, empathy, and social justice orientations in society (Gul & Ahmad, 2023; Gul et al., 2023).

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Overall, the study highlights the importance of media coverage in shaping public opinion and constructing narratives, especially when it comes to conflicts with humanitarian implications. By examining the perspective of the United Nations through the lens of International Humanitarian Law and the Geneva Convention, the study contributes to a better understanding of how international organizations such as the United Nations address complex geopolitical issues while striving to uphold the principles of impartiality and humanitarianism. The findings highlight the need for continued efforts to promote peace, protect civilians and address the root causes of conflicts to prevent further escalation and suffering in regions such as Gaza and Israel.

In conclusion, the study finds that UN News addressed the Gaza–Israel conflict largely through a humanitarian and international humanitarian law-oriented frame, with strong emphasis on civilian protection, humanitarian aid, ceasefire appeals, denunciation of brutality, and the urgent need to prevent further suffering. This answers the research question by showing that neutrality, peacebuilding, and humanitarian concerns were highly visible throughout the coverage, although traces of subjectivity were also evident, particularly in the differential emphasis placed on Palestinian civilian suffering and, at certain points, on Israeli victims and hostages. Overall, the findings suggest that UN News did not function as a purely detached observer; rather, it combined an institutional commitment to impartiality with a morally charged humanitarian narrative grounded in the protection of civilians, condemnation of violations, and repeated calls for peace, relief, and compliance with international humanitarian law.

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